

Phishing

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Abstract— Phishing is a cyber-attack that involves posing as a trustworthy source and obtaining confidential or private data. Phishers also take advantage of users' interest in a site's appearance by using web pages that appear to be authentic. Data acquired could be then used for fraudulent activities. This paper looks phishing in detail, the working or mechanism, the various types, and how to prevent from the attack.

I. WHAT IS PHISHING?

Phishing is one of the most common cyberattacks perpetrated by criminals, as well as one of the easiest to fall for. It's also one that can give hackers anything they need to break into their victims' personal and professional accounts.

A simple phishing attack tries to trick the victim into doing what the scammer wants. It is usually carried out over email, but the scam has now expanded beyond suspicious emails to phone calls (so-called 'vishing'), social medias, messaging platforms, and even mobile applications.

The goal and mechanics of the scams differ: for example, victims might be fooled into clicking a connection to a false web page in order to persuade them to enter personal information, at the same time more sophisticated phishing schemes may take months or even years to develop a harmony with the victim, with hackers using fake social media accounts, emails, and more to build up a resonance with the victim over months or even longer.

II. HOW DOES PHISHING WORKS?

A simple phishing attack tricks an internet user and fetches his credentials or data. The most popular way of carrying out these attacks is through emails. Because of the immense volume of emails sent daily, it's an easy attack vector for cyber criminals. Every day, around 3.7 billion people send about 269 billion emails. According to Symantec researchers, almost one out of every 2,000 emails is a phishing email, implying that 135 million attacks every day are attempted. This concludes email attacks is the most common method of phishing.

III. WHY PHISHING CALLED PHISHING?

Phishing, the general word for these scams, is a modified version of 'fishing,' except that this time the fisherman is the crook, and they're trying to trap and reel the user with their devious email lure.

IV. ORIGIN OF PHISHING?

The first instance of the term "phishing" is thought to have arisen in the mid-1990s, when software tools like 'AOHell' were used to steal data. AOL (an American web portal and online service provider) user names and passwords were stolen then. Since it was a new form of attack, users hadn't seen anything like it before, these early attacks were successful. Despite AOL's warnings to users about the dangers, phishing was popular, and it's still around after 20 years. It has remained largely unchanged in several respects for one basic reason: it works.

V. THE MECHANISM

The aim of a phishing attack is to trick the attacker into divulging sensitive details about himself or herself. The attacker or phisher imitates a legitimate website to carry out such an attack. He/she creates a malicious site using a phishing website to imitate the original website. This phishing website will collect all of the target's information and use it to create a fake website and give it to the assailant. Typically, the targets are unable to sort out the difference between legitimate and phishing websites, they will fall into the phisher's traps. The attackers in phishing attacks take several measures to obtain information.

The steps are as follows:

1. Plan
2. Compose email
3. Attack
4. Gather data
5. Fraud

The attacker begins the process by devising a strategy for the attack. The first move entails settling on a legal website to be used or imitated, as well as the victim whose data that must be collected. Following preparation comes the task of writing an email that must be sent, which should appear sincere in order to persuade the victim to provide his/her information. The third step is to deliver the written email to the recipient. The goal is then followed by the victim's detail. Only if the victim is tricked, the gathering of information process begins. The phisher has now entrapped him. Taking lead of the victims. The attacker uses this information to commit cybercrime, such as credit card fraud, fraudulent use of a credentials, burglary, and so on.

VI. TYPES OF PHISHING

Phishing can be done in different ways. Motive is always the same, what varies is the number of targets and the way used to obtain the data.

The different attack types are:

- Deceptive Phishing
- Spear Phishing
- Whaling
- Pharming

A. Deceptive Phishing

The most popular and common type is the deceptive phishing. Assailant entails posing as a legitimate website and sends the target an email. The message in the inbox contains a malicious URL or a connection will be sent to the attacker. According to the phishing website's instructions, it collects the login information, credentials, or confidential data and sends it to the attacker

B. Spear Phishing

This form of phishing is very similar to deceptive phishing. Target is the only difference here. Spear phishing is a type of phishing that only targets one person. The assailant targets a person and persuades him or her to provide confidential information. The fraudsters personalize the email for each recipient. It may contain target's details, such as the person's name, organization he or she works for, designation, and so on. The most popular outlets for spear phishing are social networking sites like LinkedIn, where they can easily collect information on the individual's occupation and other similar details.

C. Whaling

When a phisher targets a specific person, in a senior executive role, such as CEO or managerial level, it is termed as whaling. The perpetrator must be profiling the suspect for a long time before committing the crime or executing the attack. Similarly, to other styles, the attacker will send an email to the goal and try to persuade him/her to do something supplying details to the attacker. Whaling is regarded as a very dangerous attack since the people in executive bands are targeted who has access to the most sensitive information in the company.

D. Pharming

The next form of phishing is pharming. In contrast to the others, it does not target specific individuals but large number of people without having to be found out.

There are two approaches to practice pharming:

1. The first approach involves sending a code to the target via email that modifies all of the system's local host data. The host files would convert the URLs to number strings, which the device would use to access web pages. Despite entering the correct URL, the user is redirected to the malicious website.
2. The second way to practice pharming is to use a DNS Poisoning. In this approach, the domain's local host files are not corrupted, but the system's domain name table is. As a result, the goal is achieved without the user's knowledge, being routed to malicious websites.

VII. HOW TO AVERT PHISHING?

A. Keep up with Phishing Techniques

New phishing scams are constantly being created. You could fall victim to one of these modern phishing techniques if you don't keep up with them. Keep an eye out for updates on new phishing scams, you would have a much smaller chance of being snared by one if you learn about them as soon as possible. Security awareness training programs and simulated phishing for users are strongly recommended especially for IT administrators in order to keep security top of mind in the enterprise

B. Consider Your Actions Before You Click!

When you're on a reputable website, it's fine to click on links. Clicking on links in unsafe emails, adds or instant messages, on the other hand, isn't such a good idea. Before clicking on any suspicious links, hover over them. Think if they are really safe. If not sure, simply do not click.

C. Add an Anti-Phishing Toolbar

Anti-phishing toolbars can be added to most common Internet browsers. These toolbars perform fast checks on the websites you're visiting and compare them to a list of established phishing websites. The toolbar will notify you if you visit a potentially harmful website. This is an added defence against phishing scams, and it's totally free.

D. Regularly Check Your Online Accounts

If you haven't visited your online account in a while, someone might be playing with it. Do checks with each of your online accounts once in a while, even though you don't technically need to. Make it a routine to change your passwords on some basis. You can personally review your statements regularly to avoid bank phishing or credit card phishing scams. Obtain monthly financial account statements and closely review the entries to ensure no fraudulent transactions have occurred.

E. Keep Your Browser Up to Date

Security updates for common browsers are issued on a regular basis. They're made public in response to the security flaws that phishers and other hackers are bound to find and exploit. Avoid ignoring messages telling you to update your browsers. Download and install any updates as soon as they become available.

F. Use Firewalls

Good firewalls serve as barriers between you, your machine, and intruders from the outside world. There are two types of firewalls to use: a desktop firewall and a network firewall. The first one is a software type, and the second is a hardware type. Use both for better security.

G. Never Give Out Personal Details

You should not give out personal or financial information over the Internet as a general rule. When in doubt, go to the company's main website, get their phone number, and send them a call. The majority of phishing emails will guide you to a page where you must enter your credentials. A user of the Internet should never enter any sensitive information using the links given in an email or in any un-known sites.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Phishing from the very beginning have proven to be much effective in stealing data and confidential information from users and enterprises. Sadly, this continues today too. Phishing is a serious cyber-attack which needs to be taken care of. This could only be achieved if each internet user takes this into serious consideration. This study provides the working, the types, the ways and how to prevent phishing in detail. Thus, while using the internet, we could and should be more aware of the threats that hides behind, and work more wisely and safely.

IX. REFERENCES

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